

STATE BUDGET TRANSPARENCY DEFICIT: CAUSES AND CONSEQUENCES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6303603>

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The budget deficit is the amount by which budget expenditures exceed its revenues in each fiscal year.

Budget surplus is the amount of budget revenues in each fiscal year that exceeds its expenditures.

A fully balanced state budget, i.e. an unbalanced budget, is only theoretically possible. Even if the draft budget is balanced, it is almost impossible to ensure equality in the process of its implementation. Highlight the pros and cons of a budget deficit.

On the other hand, underfunding policies lead to economic growth.

On the downside, the budget deficit will lead to an increase in public debt, an increase in the tax burden, and stimulate inflation.

Budget deficit:

1. The need for large public investments in economic development.
2. Emergencies (war, major natural disasters, etc.).
3. Crisis in the economy, its collapse, inefficiency of financial and credit relations, etc. are the most dangerous and disturbing form of budget deficit, which is a reflection of the crisis in the economy, its collapse, the government's inability to control the financial situation in the country.

Budget deficit functions:

1. distribution (redistribution),
2. fundraising,
3. stimulant,
4. management.

Distinguish the following types of budget deficits:

Structural deficit is a deficit inherent in the structure of revenues and expenditures in the formation of the budget.

The natural rate of unemployment, the natural rate of GDP, as well as the budget deficit or surplus calculated for the economy in the context of tax rates and transfer payments established by applicable law. Typically, structural deficits occur as a result of fiscal policy. Voluntary fiscal policy is the government's intentional adjustment of taxes (tax rates) and government spending (programs to pay for goods and services) without inflation to ensure full employment of GDP and economic growth. to stimulate swelling.

This is the calculated difference between current government spending and revenue, given a certain unemployment (natural) rate.

Cyclical deficit is a state budget deficit as a result of declining business activity and declining tax revenues.

The difference between the deficit actually observed and the structural deficit. This deficit varies throughout the work cycle. If, in practice, the observed budget deficit is less than the structural deficit, then the difference between the structural deficit and the real deficit is called a cyclical surplus.

The operating deficit is the general deficit of the state budget, excluding the inflationary portion of interest payments to repay public debt.

Quasic (hidden) deficit state budget - as a result of quasi-quasi-(quasi-budget) activities of the Central Bank, as well as state enterprises and commercial banks.

Quasic operations include:

a) overpayment of employment rates and wage rates by state-owned enterprises through bank loans or mutual loans in excess of the market rate;

b) accumulation of a large portfolio of non-performing loans in commercial banks (overdue debts of state enterprises, soft loans to households, firms, etc.) allocated by the Central Bank in the early stages of economic reforms. These loans are mainly repaid through soft loans. Central Bank;

c) Measures to stabilize the exchange rate of the Central Bank (in a transition economy), interest-free and soft loans to the government (for the purchase of wheat, rice, coffee, etc.) and non-performing loans to commercial banks refinancing of loans. The central bank offers agricultural, industrial and housing programs at preferential rates, and so on.

The hidden budget deficit reduces the current budget deficit and public debt, which can be done purposefully (e.g., before elections), as well as within the "tight" direction of the government to the budget, which is balanced each year.

The primary deficit is the difference between the general deficit and the interest payment on the debt. With the financing of the main deficit by debt, the principal amount of debt and the ratio of its service to it increase, viz. the debt burden on the economy is increasing.

Theoretically, active and passive deficiencies are also distinguished.

Active shortages occur as a result of excessive costs. This may be due to an increase in investment in new production, which will lead to the creation of new jobs, increase employment and incomes of the population.

Passive deficit - due to a decrease in taxes and other revenues (slowdown in economic growth, low payments).

The budget deficit is considered normal, which corresponds to the inflation rate in the country. Such a budget deficit is usually covered by low-interest or non-

interest-bearing debt of the Central Bank. International standards state that there may be a budget deficit of 2-3% of GDP. Generally, a budget deficit of up to 10% of revenue is considered acceptable, while a budget deficit of more than 20% is very significant.

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